

INVERSE DESIGN OF MANUFACTURING PROCESSES USING PHYSICS-INFORMED NEURAL OPERATOR LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Machine learning-based approaches, especially neural network models, have achieved remarkable success in diverse scientific applications, where the deep neural operator (DNO) enables the learning nonlinear operators between infinite-dimensional function spaces and is able to approximate governing equations of time-dependent engineering processes. This paper presents two novel applications of DNO learning to accelerate the design of composite materials and their manufacturing processes. First, we develop a DNO-based surrogate model for finite element simulations of transient mechanical response of 3D interpenetrating phase composites (IPCs) fabricated via additive manufacturing. These IPCs consist of randomly structured metallic phases with different elastic moduli. DNO is trained using a sequence-to-sequence incremental learning approach based on 5,000 finite element simulations of an IPC beam subject to random strain loads, resulting in a 98% prediction accuracy on transient stress at various cross-sections of the IPC beam under dynamic loading. The trained DNO enables real-time prediction of mechanical properties, significantly reducing the design iterations for composites. Second, we introduce an enhanced physics-informed DNO (PIDNO+) model for predicting the particle size distribution in biomass comminution processes. PIDNO+ integrates a population balance model into a hybrid DNO+ architecture that incorporates both material and processing parameters. This integration enables high accuracy with a limited small dataset while preserving physical consistency. The shared parameter network with the embedded physical model allows for differential operation in parameter space and enables inverse design of manufacturing parameters to meet target outcomes. Both DNO applications demonstrate the potential of operator learning for fast and accurate surrogate modeling in composite material design and accelerated optimization of manufacturing processes.

1 INTRODUCTION

Although deep learning algorithms have been implemented into physical problems by many researchers [1-3], it is still challenging to solve the mapping problem between time-dependent and space-dependent functions using traditional deep neural networks (DNNs). There are, in general, two possible scenarios when we develop a DNN model for composite materials. First, if we have sufficient prior physical knowledge on the composite materials and know their governing equations explicitly, i.e., in the form of partial differential equations (PDEs), it becomes possible to encode the PDEs into the DNN, which leads to the physics-informed neural network (PINN) models [4]. Second, if we lack physical knowledge of the given composites (i.e., with three or more enforcing phases) and do not know the explicit form of its governing equations, we need to learn the implicit governing equations or operators from available observed data. This motivated the development of deep neural operator (DNO) methods [5], which learn nonlinear operators between infinite-dimensional function spaces and can

approximate governing equations of time-dependent engineering processes. Deep Operator Network (DeepONet) [6], as one type of DNO, brings a new solution to find the operators. DeepONet can learn the diverse continuous nonlinear operator between input and output, so that it can be used to solve various explicit and implicit mapping functions. In the present paper, two examples of DNO application will be introduced, including DNO acting as a surrogate of physics-based composites models in time-dependent problems, and DNO enabling inverse design of manufacturing process based on small experimental dataset.

The first example of DNO application introduced in Section 2 is on neural operator learning acting as surrogate of physics-based composite model to offer real-time prediction of transient mechanical response of composites under dynamic loading. The mechanical behavior of composites, especially under dynamic loading, is highly sensitive to their 3D structural design. However, evaluating their dynamic response subject to dynamic loading typically requires time-intensive finite element analysis (FEA) or physical testing, which can take hours to days for each design. To overcome this limitation, a DNO model is developed to learn the transient mechanical response of interpenetrating phase composites (IPCs) under dynamic strain loads. DNO consists of one trunk network to encode the domain of the output functions and one DNN or multiple DNNs to encode the discrete input function space as its branch network [7]. A 3D IPC beam composed of two metals with a Young's modulus ratio of 2.7 is used to generate training data through 5,000 FEA simulations with random strain inputs. Once trained, DNO serves as a fast and reliable surrogate to predict stress fields in seconds, greatly accelerating IPC design and optimization.

The second example of DNO application introduced in Section 3 is on inverse design of manufacturing processes based on a small experimental dataset, where an enhanced Deep Neural Operator (DNO+) model is designed to learn how comminution outcomes are influenced by a parameter space consisting of both manufacturing parameters and material properties. To reduce the reliance of DNO+ on experimental data and enable effective DNO+ training on small experimental datasets, we integrate a transport equation of a population balance model (PBM) into the DNO+ framework, creating a physics-informed enhanced deep learning operator (PIDNO+) model. PIDNO+ integrates physics into the DNO+ model to combine the strengths of deep learning and physics-based modeling, therefore, it can reduce the data requirements and improve physical consistency of the model. This integration endows the PIDNO+ model with robust predictive capabilities across diverse conditions and enables inverse design of manufacturing processes for target product features.

2 A SURROGATE OF PHYSICS-BASED COMPOSITE MODEL

We start with the introduction of the physical problem setup. As shown in Figure 1(a), an IPC beam with a cuboid structure composed of stainless steel and aluminum alloy is considered, with one fixed end and one free end, where an arbitrarily dynamic strain loading is applied to the free end. The typical dynamic strain loads created by a Gaussian random process are shown in Figure 1(b). The mechanical response of interest is the time evolution of the normal stress along the x -direction σ_{xx} inside the IPC beam, where x denotes an arbitrary location in the IPC beam. The IPC beam is set to 500 mm in length with a cross section of 100 mm by 100 mm. The beam structure is divided into 40 identical cubic subdomains, each with a side length of 50 mm. Stainless steel and aluminum alloy are randomly assigned to these cubes to form a composite beam.

When the applied strain exceeds the yield point, both the elastic and plastic responses of the constituent materials (stainless steel and aluminum alloy) with significant different elastic moduli and tensile strengths should be considered. This introduces pronounced nonlinearity into the dynamic behavior of the IPC composite beam. The elasticity of the constituent materials is determined by the Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio, while the plasticity deformation is described using a multilinear isotropic hardening model derived from available stress-strain curves [8]. As shown in Figure 1(c), under a given dynamic strain loading, the IPC beam exhibits coupled deformation modes, including bending, axial stretching/compression, and twisting, due to asymmetrical distribution of material properties within the IPC beam structure.

To simulate the dynamic mechanical response, the IPC beam is discretized using the finite element method and solved numerically using the commercial software ABAQUS. The time-evolution of stress

distribution is analysed under varying dynamic strain loadings. A time-dependent strain function is created by drawing from a random Gaussian process. To ensure smooth strain loading conditions, the strain function is modulated by a sine envelope, $\sin(\pi t)$, so that the strain applied to the free end of the IPC beam always starts from a zero strain at $t = 0$ s and ends with a zero strain at $t = 1$ s, as illustrated in Figure 1(b).

A total of 5,000 FEA simulations are performed, each corresponding to a different realization of the dynamic strain loading, to generate enough data for DNO training. Each simulation runs from $t = 0$ s to $t = 1$ s with a sampling interval $\Delta t = 0.01$ s, and generates one dataset consisting a time sequence t_i with $i = (1, 2, \dots, 101)$, a time-dependent input $Y_i = \varepsilon(t_i)$, and a time-dependent output $U_i = \sigma(\mathbf{x}, t_i)$ with \mathbf{x} being an arbitrary location inside the IPC beam. Both the branch net and the trunk net of DNO have one input layer, five hidden layers, and one output layer, with a neural network architecture of $101 \times 200 \times 200 \times 300 \times 200 \times 200 \times 101$, in which the integers represent the number of neurons in those layers. The model is trained using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001 to minimize the mean squared error (MSE) between the DNO predictions and the FEA results. Of the 5,000 datasets, 4,900 are used for training and the rest for testing. The DNO model is iteratively updated until the desired accuracy is achieved or the predefined maximum number of iterations is reached.

Figure 1: (a) Computational domain and boundary condition of an IPC beam subject to dynamic strain loading. (b) Arbitrary dynamic strain loading is created by drawing a smooth time-dependent function between 0 to 1 seconds from a Gaussian random process. (c) Coupled bending, stretching/compression, and twisting deformation of the IPC beam under strain loading.

Figure 2(a1) and 2(a2) show the stress distribution at the central cross-section (perpendicular to the x -axis) of the IPC beam at $t = 0.5$ s for the FEA simulation and DNO prediction, respectively. The DNO model achieves an average prediction accuracy of 98%. The corresponding error distribution, as shown in Figure 2(a3), reveals that the prediction error is minimal in the central region and increases toward the edges. This pattern of error distribution could be attributed to the higher material uniformity in the central area and increased heterogeneity near the edge of the structure. The maximum error occurs in the upper-right corner, which is consistent with the fact that edge region has high structural complexity and freedom due to the boundary condition - only one end of the IPC beam is fixed. Under compressive loading, this boundary condition allows the structure to bend and twist simultaneously, as observed in Figure 1(c), which makes the stress distribution more complicated.

At the end of the dynamic loading, i.e., $t = 1$ s, although the applied strain at the free end returns to zero, residual stresses remain in the structure, as shown in Figure 2(b1). These residual stresses arise due to irreversible plastic deformation accumulated during the dynamic loading process. Interestingly, even if the applied strain passes through the zero point one or more times, different internal stress states may result each time due to the path-dependent plasticity. This reflects the fact that the process is both time- and space-dependent, making it hard to predict using traditional neural networks. In general, the trained DNO model demonstrates robust prediction capability, achieving stress prediction accuracies ranging from 95% to 99% across various cross-sections when compared to FEA results.

This establishes the DNO as an effective surrogate of physics-based FEA models for real-time prediction of the transient mechanical behavior of composite structures under dynamic loading, which will significantly accelerate computational analysis in composite design and material discovery.

Figure 2: DNO as a surrogate of FEA model to predict the cross-section stress distribution. (a1) and (b1) show the transient stress distribution of a selected cross-section from FEA model at 0.5 s and 1.0 s respectively. (a2) and (b2) illustrate the DNO prediction of stress distribution of the selected cross-section at 0.5 s and 1.0 s respectively. (a3) and (b3) show the prediction error distribution within the cross-section at 0.5 s and 1.0 s respectively.

3 INVERSE DESIGN OF MANUFACTURING PROCESSES

3.1 An Enhanced Physics-informed Deep Neural Operator (PIDNO+) Model

To enable inverse design of a manufacturing process by optimizing adjustable manufacturing parameters, we must enable differential operations in the manufacturing parameter space. To this end, an enhanced deep neural operator (DNO+) model developed by Lu et al. [9] is adopted to map the relationship between the system’s input and output while incorporating additional variables that impact the mapping. The DNO+ model consists of a trunk net, a branch net, and a parameter net, as shown in Figure 3. In particular, the branch network takes the cumulative mass distribution with reference to the particle size sequence as input, the trunk net handles the particle size sequence through the entire comminution process, and the parameter network correlates the impact of important feed material properties and manufacturing parameters on the resultant particle size distribution (PSD) of comminuted material.

The primary input of the biomass comminution DNO+ model is the feed-in cumulative mass distribution Φ_{in} with reference to a particle size sequence \mathbf{x} , and the influence parameters \mathbf{p} . The cumulative mass distribution Φ_{out} as output is then expressed as

$$\Phi_{out} = \mathcal{F}(\Phi_{in}) \cdot \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{x}) + \mathcal{L}(\mathbf{p}) \cdot \mathcal{R}(\mathbf{x}), \tag{1}$$

where \mathcal{F} , \mathcal{L} , and \mathcal{R} represent different operators and are approximated by the neural network. Here, a fully connected neural network is used in the trunk net to process each input feature independently, while convolutional neural networks are used in the branch and parameter networks to extract features from spatially structured data by virtue of their shared-weight architecture. The introduction of additional parameter networks enables the DNO+ model to consider the impact of material or process

parameters on system results and thus more effectively capture the relationship between system input and output.

To address the challenge of training DNO+ on limited experimental data, a physical model is integrated into the DNO+ structure to reduce the data requirements for training the DNO+ model. In this work, a population balance model (PBM) [10] for modeling particle breakage and the evolution of PSD is used to constrain DNO+ training. The core concept of PBM is to track the statistical distribution of a population of particles over time or space, accounting for key phenomena such as breakage and aggregation. PBM describes how larger particles disintegrate into smaller ones under the influence of mechanical stress (e.g., compression, shear, or impact), which is suitable for this biomass comminution DNO+ model.

Let the breakage matrix of PBM be X , and the classification matrix for considering the effects of screen size and passing efficiency be C . The mapping function between the feed PSD (F_{PSD}) and the product PSD of milled materials (P_{PSD}) can be expressed as

$$P_{\text{PSD}} = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} C \cdot (I-C)^{k-1} \cdot X^k \cdot F_{\text{PSD}}. \quad (2)$$

However, Eq. (2) lacks a description of the impact of material properties or manufacturing parameters on the system. To address this limitation, the advantage of high-dimensional expression of neural networks can be used to establish a complex relationship by allowing the matrices X and C to be functions of material properties and manufacturing parameters.

Figure 3: The structure of physics-informed deep neural operator (PIDNO+) model. The PIDNO+ model combines the population balance model (PBM) and DNO+ and establishes the connection between PBM and model parameters through neural networks. The total loss of the PIDNO+ model is the summation of data loss and physical loss. Data loss enables the model to learn from the available data, while physical loss aids the model in learning from the physical-based model.

Figure 3 illustrates the structure of a physics-informed deep neural operator (PIDNO+) model by integrating a PBM into a DNO+ model. The original breakage matrix X in PBM is defined by the breakage function B and the breakage probability S . From Eq. (2), it can be observed that if a connection can be established between matrix X and parameters p , which represent feed material properties and manufacturing parameters, the influence of these parameters on the system can be determined. In the PIDNO+ model, X is a matrix with size (b, n, n) , where b is the batch size and n the data length. After a flattening process, X changes into X_{flat} with size (b, n^2) . The influence of parameter net is introduced in the fully connected neural network, which establishes a relationship between a parameter dependent breakage matrix $X(p)$ and X_{flat} . Therefore, the breakage matrix X in Eq. (2) can be replaced by $X(p)$, resulting in the milled materials P_{PSD} various with respect to the parameters p .

The overall loss function L_{total} in PIDNO+ is formulated by combining three key components: the data-fitting loss between the real data U_{real} and the DNO+ model data $U_{\text{DNO+}}$, the data-fitting loss

between the real data U_{real} and the physical model data U_{phys} , and the consistency loss between the DNO+ model data $U_{\text{DNO+}}$ and the physical model data U_{phys} ,

$$L_{\text{total}} = \lambda_1 \cdot \text{MSE}(U_{\text{real}}, U_{\text{DNO+}}) + \lambda_2 \cdot \text{MSE}(U_{\text{real}}, U_{\text{phys}}) + \text{MSE}(U_{\text{DNO+}}, U_{\text{phys}}), \quad (3)$$

where λ_1 and λ_2 serve as weights to determine the significance of different losses. $\text{MSE}(U_{\text{real}}, U_{\text{DNO+}})$ ensures the accuracy of the data-driven part in fitting the data within the entire model. $\text{MSE}(U_{\text{real}}, U_{\text{phys}})$ helps the embedded PBM find suitable built-in parameters. $\text{MSE}(U_{\text{DNO+}}, U_{\text{phys}})$ ensures the auxiliary role of the physical model in the prediction results of the PIDNO+ model.

3.2 Inverse Design of Manufacturing Processes

To validate the PIDNO+ model proposed in this paper, corn stalks were used as an example and experiments were conducted on the comminution process of corn stalks. The material was prepared to have different moisture content levels that represent typical ranges found in corn stover feedstocks in the U.S. Midwest and South. The preparation involved conditioning the corn stalks to achieve the desired moisture levels before comminution. A G1635 Granulator knife mill was configured with a motor capable of operating at different frequencies to adjust the blade tip speed. Different output frequencies were employed from 40 Hz to 60 Hz, corresponding to blade tip speeds ranging from $6.5 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ to $9.8 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. Different discharge screen sizes were chosen to investigate their impact on the particle size distribution of the comminuted material.

To test the feasibility of the model and its data requirements, training and testing datasets need to be prepared. The information contained in one training dataset includes distribution of feed mass versus sieve size, feed moisture content, discharge screen size, and distribution of discharged mass versus sieve size. When the DNO+ model is trained with sufficient data, i.e., 400 datasets, it demonstrates high prediction accuracy for any input within the feasible domain. However, in many cases, sufficient data may not always be available, and the performance of DNO+ without a physical model will be negatively affected. Figure 4(a) shows the prediction results of DNO+ model trained on 100 datasets. It can be observed that although the prediction results generally follow the trend, they deviate a little from the actual values. More extremely, some data points may exceed 100%, rendering the results physically meaningless. In contrast, the PIDNO+ model, trained on a much smaller dataset, achieves an average prediction accuracy of 98% without any values exceeding 100% of cumulative mass, as shown in Figure 4(b). This high accuracy is attributed to the support of the integrated physical model, which not only requires less training data but also conforms to certain physical rules.

Figure 4: Comparison of the prediction results on the cumulative mass percentage changed with various sizes of sieve: (a) DNO+ with 100 datasets, (b) PIDNO+ with 50 datasets.

The additional parameter network in PIDNO+ enables differential operations in the parameters space, which includes the influence of feed material properties and manufacturing parameters. The trained PIDNO+ model will approximate the nonlinear mapping between the PSD of feed material,

moisture content, screen size, and the resulting PSD of the milled material, which can be optimized to determine the ideal combination of the feed material PSD, moisture levels and screen size to achieve the desired product PSD. Figure 5 demonstrates an inverse design of corn stalks comminution process using PIDNO+. By giving an expected cumulative particle size distribution (PSD) and a feed material PSD, PIDNO+ can determine the moisture content of 30.71% and a screen size of 20.52 mm for the milling machines to produce a cumulative PSD of milled materials consistent with the expected PSD. As a result, the corresponding cumulative PSD outputs are successfully obtained for each case. The real-time prediction of comminution products and inverse design of manufacturing parameters not only enhance manufacturing process control but also reduces energy consumption and operational costs by minimizing trial-and-error experimentation.

Figure 5: Inverse design of comminution manufacturing parameters. Given an expected cumulative particle size distribution (PSD) with a feed material PSD, PIDNO+ predicts that the moisture content should be adjusted to 30.71% and a screen size of 20.52 mm, which produces a cumulative PSD of milled materials consistent with the expected PSD.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Two significant advancements in modeling and prediction of complex material systems using neural operator learning were presented. First, a Deep Neural Operator (DNO) model was developed to serve as a superfast and accurate surrogate for finite element analysis (FEA) in predicting transient mechanical response of interpenetrating phase composites (IPCs) under dynamic loading. Unlike conventional FEA-based methods that require repeated simulations for different loading conditions, the trained DNO can offer real-time prediction of mechanical responses for arbitrary strain sequences. The use of arbitrary random strain loads in DNO training improves its ability to be generalized for extended temporal inputs. The high accuracy of DNO in predicting stress distributions promises to significantly accelerate composites design and material optimization. Future work may involve integrating Bayesian neural networks [11] for improved uncertainty quantification in noisy data scenarios.

Second, an enhanced Physics-Integrated Deep Neural Operator (PIDNO+) model with an additional parameter network was introduced for predicting particle size distributions (PSD) in a comminution process, offering a flexible and interpretable deep learning framework by integrating a DNO+ model with a physics-based population balance model (PBM). The PIDNO+ model reduces data dependency by embedding physical laws directly into the learning architecture. By incorporating multi-physics relationships and empirical laws from PBM into DNO+, the model captures the influence of material properties and manufacturing parameters on particle breakage with improved generality and adaptability across different regimes, which were validated on experimental comminution data of flexible materials (corn stalks). PIDNO+ offers fast and interpretable predictions of PSD evolution in comminution processes, in which the differentiable parameter network enables the inverse design of manufacturing processes through optimizing feed material properties and manufacturing parameters.

With differentiable parameter network for optimizing manufacturing parameters, this DNO+ inverse design framework will be applied to manufacturing processes of composites, including the inverse design of thermoforming processes for carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites [12], and the inverse design of injection molding parameters for thermoplastic composites [13], based on experimental data generated at the University of Delaware Center for Composite Materials.

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